

NOTES

500 nm, 700 nm at 10 nm, 20 nm or 25 nm intervals. The results are shown in Table 2.

Composition of the chelates :

The composition of the metal chelates have been determined spectrophotometrically using the method of continuous variations⁸ and the mole ratio method⁹. In all the systems studied the composition has been found to be 1 : 1 (metal : ligand). The results of composition are also included in Table 3.

Evaluation of stability constants :

The conditional stability constants have been determined by the method of Dey¹⁰ *et al* and the mole ratio method at 25° and at pH of study. The results are included in Table 3.

TABLE 3

COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BPGR CHELATES

Chelation system	Composition Metal : BPGR	log k	Method
Sc(III)-BPGR	1 : 1	5.4	(i)
		6.6	(ii)
Y(III)-BPGR	"	5.9	(i)
		6.9	(ii)
La(III)-BPGR	"	5.3	(i)
		6.6	(ii)
Ce(III)-BPGR	"	5.2	(i)
		5.5	(ii)
Pr(III)-BPGR	"	5.1	(i)
		5.8	(ii)
Nd(III)-BPGR	"	5.1	(i)
		6.1	(ii)
Sm(III)-BPGR	"	5.0	(i)
		5.8	(ii)
Eu(III)-BPGR	"	4.5	(i)
		5.9	(ii)
Gd(III)-BPGR	"	5.2	(i)
		6.8	(ii)
Tb(III)-BPGR	"	4.3	(i)
		6.5	(ii)
Dy(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		5.2	(ii)
Ho(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		6.2	(ii)
Er(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		6.4	(ii)

(i) Method of Dey *et al.* (ii) Mole Ratio method.

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Chalcones. XV : Potential Germicides Derived from 2-Methoxy-1-Acetonaphthone

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AMONG the different fields of study in Chalcone Chemistry, their aspect of antimicrobial property was most fascinating to modern chemists. As early in 1948, Schraufstatter¹⁻² showed the path, that chalcones are capable of destroying disease germs. Later researches proved³⁻⁷ that these compounds having different substituents *viz.*, hydroxy, methoxy, chloro, bromo, etc. either in ketone part or aldehyde were found to possess bacteriostatic, anthelmintic, fungicidal, carcinogenic, cardiovascular, etc. activity. Moreover, Wilson and coworkers⁸ have observed that methoxy chalcones can check up the destruction of adrenaline. It may be due to the fact that ethylenic linkage has the property to react with certain cellular constituents. This has prompted the present author to synthesize methoxy chalcone analogues.

The present investigation is an attempt to synthesize methoxy naphthalene chalcone analogues by Claisen-Schmidt condensation and to study their antimicrobial activity against gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*), gram negative bacteria (*E. coli*) and *A. niger* by agar-cup method.

In order to achieve this end 2-methoxy-1-acetonaphthone was condensed with different benzaldehydes in presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (Table 1). The identity of the compounds was established by preparing a few 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives, colour reaction with concentrated H₂SO₄ and elemental analyses.

The germicidal and fungicidal activity was tested by agar-cup method at a concentration of 100±10 µg/ml. against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. niger* and compared with benzoic acid. The inocula were prepared from stationary culture and inhibition of growth was checked at an incubation temperature of (32°±2°) after 24 hrs. No encouraging results were obtained.

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TABLE I PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-METHOXY-1-NAPHTHYL CHALCONEAS

R	Colour and Crystal form	M.P***°C		Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Yield %	Time of reaction (hours)	%C		%H	
		Chalcone	2,4-DNP				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
2-OH	brown globules	165	259	black	34	49	78.72	78.94	4.91	5.26
3-OH	dull yellow plates	203	—	brown	30	50	72.65	78.94	5.57	5.26
4-OH	light violet prisms	161	234	violet	32	50	78.83	78.94	5.69	5.26
2-Cl	yellow globules	142	—	blood-red	89	24	74.61	74.40	4.91	4.65
3-Cl	yellow needles	140	217	red	81	24	74.52	74.40	4.38	4.65
4-Cl	pale yellow needles	153	—	orange	87	26	74.28	74.40	4.41	4.65
2-Me*	orange clusters	142	231	dark-red	62	37	83.72	83.45	6.09	5.96
3-Me	lemon yellow plates	121	—	violet	59	30	83.68	83.45	5.61	5.96
4-Me*	yellow prisms	114	—	pink	65	38	83.18	83.45	5.75	5.96
2-OMe*	yellow needles	130	210	blood-red	59	41	79.53	79.25	5.38	5.66
3-OMe*	lemon yellow plates	107	247	cherry-red	51	42	79.87	79.25	5.93	5.66
4-OMe	yellow clusters	144	—	blood-red	63	42	79.13	79.25	5.32	5.66
2,3-O(CH ₃) ₂ *	yellow prisms	127	—	pink	60	28	75.31	75.86	6.15	5.74
2,4-(OMe) ₂	yellow needles	148	—	orange	63	28	76.18	75.86	5.46	5.74
3-OMe-4-OH	orange clusters	137	—	violet	51	27	75.56	75.23	5.93	5.67
3-OMe-4-OH-5-Br	dull yellow needles	119	238	red	67	42	61.24	60.87	4.68	4.34
4-NMe ₂ *	orange prisms	150	—	red	58	30	81.06	79.77	6.59	6.34

* crystallised from ethylacetate
 ** All melting points are uncorrected.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-methoxy-1-naphthyl chalcone analogue :

These chalcone analogues were prepared by adding, saturated solution of caustic potash in 10% aqueous ethyl alcohol, dropwise to an equimolar alcoholic mixture of 2-methoxy-1-acetonaphthone and required aryl aldehyde at room temperature. The deposited compound was purified by repeated crystallisations from ethyl alcohol (Table I).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones derivatives were prepared by treating an ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution of chalcone with the reagent at 80° and purified by crystallisation from ethylacetate (Table I). All melting points are uncorrected.

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Phytochemical Studies on *Saussurea sacra* Edgew

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THE genus *Saussurea* is represented by well over nine species in Kashmir¹, and only few of these have so far been chemically analysed². *Saussurea sacra* Edgew, locally known as "Jogiraj or Jogipathsha" has been extensively used as a medicinal herb by sadhus and hakims³, for a number of chronic ailments like stomach ulcers, piles, bronchites, cardiac disorders, nose bleeding, impotency etc. However a dig in its chemical composition has so far